

A CORRELATION STUDY OF SIMULATED HIPPARCOS ASTROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

Parallaxes and proper motions derived from Hipparcos will have errors which are statistically correlated between different stars, especially within a small area as in a stellar cluster. Taking the average of n stars, *e.g.* to get the mean parallax of a cluster, will therefore not bring about the expected $n^{-0.5}$ improvement. The effect has been studied by statistical analysis of the output catalogue resulting from a simulated two-year mission comprising all the 114,488 stars in the preliminary input catalogue version IC1. It appears that improvements of the order of $n^{-0.35}$ are probably more realistic. Some general results on the expected astrometric accuracy as function of magnitude and position are also presented.

Key words: space astrometry, parallax, accuracy, cluster

1. Introduction

A question certain to be asked by many future users of the Hipparcos catalogue is: How accurate are the astrometric data? There is however no simple answer to that question. The word 'accuracy' is quantitatively meaningful only in relation to some statistical model purporting to describe certain properties of the catalogue errors. Depending on the actual application that the user has in mind, the relevant properties vary and a model useful in one investigation may be totally inadequate for another. Each astrometric datum in the Hipparcos catalogue will for instance be accompanied by an estimate of its standard error. Tacitly, this seems to imply that the datum (a trigonometric parallax, say) in some sense resembles an independent random value drawn from a normal population with mean value equal to the true parallax and with the stated standard deviation. This implicit assumption of *normalcy*, *unbiasedness*, and *independence* may be justified in simple investigations of individual stars. In any statistical study one must however consider the possible existence of *outliers*, of a (possibly colour and position dependent) *bias*, and of statistical *correlation* between data for different stars and between the different parameters of the same star.

It is extremely difficult to make quantitative predictions about outliers and biases. The reason is that they are typically the result of some unexpected defects in the reduction model *vis-à-vis* the real data. Provided that every effort is made to include in the reduction model all the effects we can think of, it is somewhat in the nature of biases that they cannot be predicted by the use of similar models. Statistical correlations are an

entirely different matter. These are in principle easy to calculate from a linearised reduction model, where the astrometric errors are expressed as functions of the supposedly uncorrelated observation noise. In standard least-squares estimation the correlations are simply obtained from the inverse normal equations matrix. Due to the size of the problem, this is however impracticable in the present case. Alternatively, the correlations can be estimated by statistical analysis of the errors resulting from a reduction of simulated input data, in which uncorrelated observation noise was applied by means of a random number generator. That is the method used for the present study.

Using special simulation software, observations covering an interval of two years were generated in the form of one-dimensional angular normal points (abscissae). Details of the simulation are given in Section 3. The observations were fed into the reduction programs developed at Lund Observatory for the last phase of the Hipparcos data treatment, producing the astrometric parameters for all programme stars. The results were compared with the 'true' data used in the simulation and the errors subjected to statistical analysis. This concerned in particular the correlation of parallaxes or proper motions within small fields. Results of this study are reported in Section 4, while Section 5 contains some more general results on the astrometric accuracy.

2. Standard error of a mean datum

It is of considerable interest to know how accurately one can determine the *mean parallax* or *mean proper motion* of a stellar cluster or association. The answer depends critically on the degree of correlation among the data for individual stars. Positive correlations are generally expected within any small area of the sky (because there is a tendency for these stars to be observed relative to each other, as they often appear together in the instrument's field of view); the mean datum is then less accurate than the (naïvely) expected $n^{-0.5}$ improvement of the standard error.

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ be the parallax errors for n different stars supposed to have the same true parallax. (The equations below apply equally to the components of the proper motion.) The error in the (unweighted) mean parallax is

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i x_i \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the individual measurements are unbiased, $E(x_i) = 0$, and of equal variance $E(x_i^2) = \sigma^2$, we find that the mean parallax is also unbiased with variance

$$e^2 = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_i \sum_j E(x_i x_j) = (\sigma^2/n) \left[1 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \rho_{ij} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $\rho_{ij} = E(x_i x_j)/\sigma^2$ is the correlation between x_i and x_j . With

$$\langle \rho \rangle = [n(n-1)]^{-1} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \rho_{ij} \quad (3)$$

denoting the mean correlation between any two stars in the group, we may write the *improvement factor* (due to the averaging of data for n stars) as

$$e/\sigma = \left[\frac{1}{n} + \frac{n-1}{n} \langle \rho \rangle \right]^{-1/2} \quad (4)$$

If the mean correlation is zero, we get of course the expected $n^{-0.5}$ improvement. If the mean correlation is positive, the improvement will never be better than $\sqrt{\langle \rho \rangle}$, no matter how many stars are included in the averaging.

It ought to be mentioned that positive correlation is not always a disadvantage. To determine cluster memberships, for instance, we are particularly interested in *differential* parallaxes or proper motions. These may in fact be somewhat improved by the correlation.

3. Simulation and reduction

It would not be feasible to simulate, for an observation period of several years, the raw data as they are produced by the satellite and subsequently to feed them through the whole reduction chain. Instead, certain intermediate quantities known as the *star abscissae* were simulated directly, thus skipping the first few steps of the reduction chain. The abscissae appear in the reductions as a kind of normal points summarizing the astrometric information gathered in an interval of about 10 hours, or five revolutions of the satellite. They are one-dimensional angular coordinates along a *reference great circle* specifically defined for each 10 hour interval. (For an overview of the reductions, see *e.g.* Perryman, 1987.) The simulation is nevertheless believed to be sufficiently detailed for a meaningful quantitative analysis of the results. Some of its features are:

- the observing programme is modelled by a first possible version of the Input Catalogue (IC1), which comprises 114,488 stars (Turon, 1986);
- the 'nominal scanning law' adopted for the real mission determines the occurrences, throughout the mission, of each programme star within the 0.9×0.9 deg² field of view, taking into account field occultations by the Earth and Moon;
- a gaussian pseudo-random generator is used to generate abscissa errors with standard deviation computed according to each star's magnitude, colour, and (non-occulted) observing time. The errors include a cyclic correlation depending on the abscissa difference between stars observed on the same reference great circle.

The assumption of cyclic correlation along each reference great circle is crucial to the present investigation, since the spatial correlation found in the final astrometric data is due mainly to this effect. Such correlation was discussed already 10 years ago by the present author, but only during the last year has it become possible to estimate it directly by statistical analysis of realistic outputs from the great-circle reduction process (Lindgren and Petersen, 1985). Fig. 1 shows the result of such an analysis of 1964 abscissae obtained from a reduction performed by Petersen (1987, private communication) of some 78,000 simulated grid coordinates. The abscissa errors were analyzed by binning all $1964 \times 1963/2$ data pairs according to the abscissa difference ν (in the range 0 to 180°) and calculating the sample correlation coefficient for each half-degree bin. Several interesting features appear in this correlogram, most notably the peaks at small multiples of the basic angle (58°): $\nu = 0^\circ, 58^\circ, 116^\circ, 174^\circ, 128^\circ (= 360^\circ - 4 \times 58^\circ)$, perhaps also $70^\circ (= 360^\circ - 5 \times 58^\circ)$. The width of each peak is about 3° (FWHM).

In order to simulate abscissa errors with a cyclic correlation similar to the one shown in Fig. 1, without actually carrying out the great-circle reductions (which would be much too time-consuming), we need however a simpler description of the correlation. I have used the analytical model developed in Høyer *et al.* (1981), which is based on a completely regular distribution of N stars along the reference great circle. From equations (A.12) and (A.15) in that paper one derives the following expression for the theoretical correlation coefficient r as function of the abscissa difference (v) between two stars observed on the same reference great circle:

$$r(v) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N/2} 1/K_i \right]^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N/2} \cos(iv)/K_i \quad (5)$$

where

$$K_i = 2(m-1) - 4 \cos(i\gamma) \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ (\text{odd})}}^{m-1} \frac{m-k}{m} \cos(\pi ki/N) - 4 \sum_{\substack{k=2 \\ (\text{even})}}^{m-1} \frac{m-k}{m} \cos(\pi ki/N) \quad (6)$$

γ is the basic angle and m the number of stars simultaneously inside the (double) field of view ($m = \Phi N/\pi$, if Φ is the size of the FOV). The relevant parameters are $N = 2000$, $\gamma = 58^\circ$, and $\Phi = 0.9^\circ$ ($m = 10$). A practically useful approximation of $r(v)$ is obtained by retaining only the 16 or so most significant harmonics in (5), *viz.*, $i = 6, 31, 25, 37, 19, 12, 56, 62, 50, 43, 13, 18, 68, 44, 87, 81$; the resulting correlogram is shown in Fig. 2. All significant peaks in Fig. 1 are well reproduced by the theoretical curve, which is therefore adopted for the present simulation. In practice, cyclic correlation is introduced by applying only 84% of the abscissa variance as an independent gaussian error, and the remaining 16% [$= r(0)$] as a sum of 16 harmonics with amplitudes in proportion to $1/K_i$ and random phases (using of course the same phases for all abscissae on the same reference great circle).

A two-year interval starting on J1990.0 was simulated, comprising 1644 reference great circles with a total of 3.2 million abscissae measurements of the 114,488 stars in IC1. The data were written on magnetic tapes in precisely the format that will be used for input to the last phase of the real reductions to be performed at Lund Observatory. This phase, known as Step 2/3 or the sphere reconstitution and determination of astrometric parameters (Lindegren and Söderhjelm, 1985), provides an estimate of the five astrometric parameters for each programme star, and of the corresponding 5×5 covariance matrices. Knowing also the 'true' values of all parameters (*viz.*, the values used to generate the observations), a list of the astrometric errors was produced, including also the formal standard error of each datum. This formed the main input to the analysis described below.

4. Results of the correlation analysis

The results reported in this section were exclusively obtained from the analysis of *parallax errors*. (Theoretical arguments as well as some smaller test computations indicate

Figure 1. Cyclic correlation of abscissa errors, calculated from a set of 1964 abscissae obtained by geometrical great-circle reduction of simulated grid coordinates. The sample correlation coefficient is shown as function of the angular separation between the stars. The standard error of each correlation coefficient is about 0.015. This curve should be compared with the theoretical correlogram in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Cyclic correlation of abscissae as predicted by the analytical formula (5) (retaining only the 16 dominant harmonics). This model is adopted for simulating correlated abscissae used as input for the determination of astrometric parameters.

essentially identical results for the proper motion components.) The analysis was made by binning pairs of programme stars according to angular separation and calculating the sample correlation coefficient for each bin. However, for practical reasons only a subset (about 1%) of the more than 6 billion possible pairs were actually used.

Fig. 3 shows the average parallax correlation for separations up to 15° . Additional data at larger separations are given in Fig. 4. Up to a few degrees the curves are quite similar to the assumed abscissa correlation (Fig. 2), decreasing from a maximum of 0.16 for very close stars to slightly negative values between 2.5° and 8° , followed by a weak maximum around 11° . Remarkably enough, there is no evidence of a correlation peak for parallaxes at 58° separation, even though that peak is very prominent for the abscissae.

Due to the large differences in the geometry of scanning across different parts of the sky (*cf.* Fig. 2 in Lindegren, 1982), one would expect significant variations of the correlation function with ecliptic latitude (β) and (at least for $|\beta| < 45^\circ$) with the position angle of the pair. Surprisingly, however, the spatial correlation of parallax errors appears to be quite homogeneous and isotropic. This is shown in Figs. 5 and 6, where a division was made according to the mean latitude and orientation of each pair. We may therefore consider the mean curve (Fig. 3) to be representative for all parts of the sky and all directions. For separations greater than 15° the correlation is practically zero.

Using the curve in Fig. 3 for ρ_{ij} together with equations (3) and (4) it is now possible to evaluate the improvement factor ϵ/σ to be expected for any configuration of n stars. To get an idea of how important the correlations are, I have computed the improvement factor for a large number of random configurations. Assuming for simplicity uniform distribution of stars within a certain radius (R), one finds the mean improvement factor in Fig. 7, depending on the number of stars (n) for which the astrometric data are

Figure 7. Mean improvement factor (4) for circular clusters, shown as function of the number of stars (n) and the mean density of cluster stars ($0, 1.4, 2.8, 5.6 \text{ deg}^{-2}$). The line for zero density follows the $n^{-0.5}$ law; the dashed line shows a tentative $n^{-0.35}$ law.

averaged, and on the mean density of stars in the configuration $[n/2\pi(1-\cos R) \simeq n/\pi R^2]$. Compared with the line for uncorrelated data ($\epsilon/\sigma = n^{-0.5}$), the maximum loss amounts to a factor 1.7 in standard error (for $n \simeq 25$ to 100) at the mean density of IC1 (2.8 stars deg^{-2}). The dashed line in Fig. 7 illustrates the relation $\epsilon/\sigma = n^{-0.35}$, which could perhaps be used as a rule of thumb for typical clusters in the Hipparcos programme.

5. Standard errors of individual positions, proper motions and parallaxes

As a by-product of the simulations used for the correlation study, I have also computed the typical standard error of each astrometric parameter as function of the ecliptic latitude (β) and the stellar magnitude in the Hipparcos system $[m_h \simeq m_v + 0.38(B-V)]$. Because the simulations only cover 2.0 years, it was necessary to transform the standard errors to the nominal mission length of 2.5 years through application of a factor $\sqrt{0.8}$ for the positions and parallaxes, and $(\sqrt{0.8})^3$ for the proper motions. Table 1 shows the standard errors as sky averages versus magnitude, while Table 2 gives the multiplicative factor to be applied as function of the ecliptic latitude.

m_H	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	
$\sigma_\alpha \cos \delta$	0.90	0.93	1.00	1.11	1.27	1.56	1.97
σ_δ	0.77	0.80	0.86	0.95	1.08	1.32	1.67
$\sigma_{\mu\alpha} \cos \delta$	1.34	1.39	1.49	1.64	1.88	2.30	2.91
$\sigma_{\mu\delta}$	1.08	1.12	1.20	1.33	1.52	1.84	2.34
σ_π	1.15	1.19	1.28	1.42	1.64	2.00	2.54

Table 1. Standard errors (in milliarcsec) of the five astrometric parameters as function of stellar magnitude in the Hipparcos system. The values are averages for all stars in IC1 within each magnitude interval (the first and last columns are for magnitudes <6.5 and >11.5 respectively).

$ \beta $	6°	12°	17°	24°	30°	37°	44°	53°	64°	
α	1.34	1.32	1.29	1.23	1.14	1.02	0.85	0.65	0.71	0.75
δ	1.11	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.07	1.03	0.96	0.87	0.87	0.89
π	1.22	1.22	1.20	1.17	1.12	1.06	0.97	0.83	0.74	0.67

Table 2. Variation of standard errors with the ecliptic latitude (equal area zones). The table gives the factor to be applied on the sky averages in Table 1. The factors are practically independent of magnitude, and the same factor can be used for proper motions as for the corresponding components of the position.

Note that the tabulated standard errors in position are valid only *very* close to the mean epoch of observation (mid-mission); at the beginning or end of the mission the position errors are for instance twice as large.

The standard errors reported here are somewhat smaller than the usually quoted 'canonical' figure of about 2 mas (milliarcsec) or 2 mas yr^{-1} for stars brighter than 9th magnitude. The present study is (as far as I know) the first accuracy assessment based on a completely realistic observing list (IC1) and a rigorous full-scale treatment of more than a half million astrometric parameters. Several error sources have been left out, among them chromaticity and veiling glare. On the other hand there are also certain margins on the photon count rates and in the abscissa error budget. In the end I want to stress that estimates given in this paper are purely my own and that no official status should therefore be attached to them.

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